

INTERACTION OF SUPERVISION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' LEARNING PROCESS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation

It is known that monitoring and analyzing the educational process is one of the main forms of leading the work of the pedagogical team. The main purpose of control and analysis is not to find shortcomings, to confirm the state of work, but to improve their teaching methodology through the correct planning and rational organization of the educational process carried out by teachers, to eliminate errors and shortcomings in their work in a timely manner, and to give them the necessary methodological recommendations[1].

Key words: monitoring, conducting, educational process, control, supervision, pedagogical process, control activities, current control, midterm, motivation, backwash effect, cognitive, affective, objective.

Some researchers emphasized the need to understand the characteristics of human nature, his natural needs, the ability to take into account the mechanisms and laws of mental activity and personality development in the pedagogical process. A similar point of view was expressed by I.I. Davidov and he emphasized the need to take into account the student's psychotype in the process of interaction within the educational process and supervision [2]. According to the results of the pedagogical experiment, it can be said that the control performed not by the teacher, but by the neighboring student is perceived more calmly. Thus, D.I. Mendeleev gave an example from his life to prove his point. The student has the opportunity to be evaluated in terms of a personal approach rather than in terms of the systematic approach used during the current supervision. The effectiveness of educational activities directly depends on how consciously the student approaches solving the main issues, the importance of the goals set for his personality, and conducting control activities helps to clarify the student's understanding of the correct reference.

The psychological component is important in conducting control. Control, especially intermediate control related to the official indicator (sign) of mastering the studied material and the formation of competencies, is perceived by students as a punitive measure, which negatively affects the ease of self-awareness and self-awareness of each student, as a result of which it is

extrapolated to the microclimate of the entire group. Current control is the main part of the methodological support of each lesson, both systematic and planned, therefore inevitable; the regularity of behavior helps to perceive it as an element of support in the process of cooperation between the teacher and students in the audience, as a result of which the educational function of control is realized.

Control, and especially border control, is traditionally viewed from two opposing positions. Current control does not cause strong controversy among researchers, practitioners or students, because it is not perceived as a threat by students, it does not have a formal component (no assessment), it is not carried out with the participation of an expert commission. This is a preventive component of the learning process, which the student does not always notice. The need for mid-term control or rejection is being seriously discussed. That being said, the debate has historical roots. Scientist and teacher D.I. Mendeleev was a supporter of canceling exams, equating them to a lottery, and did not see any logical basis for their conduct, in addition, he considered it a harmful phenomenon that hinders the development of the science of pedagogy. At the current stage, the problem has mass resonance. In addition to teachers, psychologists, testologists, methodologists, programmers and other specialists indirectly related to the educational process and control are also involved in its solution.

Supporters of rejection of midterm control as an integral part of the university pedagogical process defend their opinion and give the following arguments. First, the control makes the subject nervous, which can ultimately have a negative effect on the results. Secondly, when preparing for the exam, the focus is on the formal delivery factor. Mark Zelman, an American expert on the development of the measurement of knowledge control, in a number of his speeches and publications, emphasizes the need to create a new test, for which it is enough not to know, but to think. Thirdly, midterm control aimed at checking a specific subject and course is carried out by checking individual, often secondary elements that do not reflect the full picture of the student's mastery of the entire system of knowledge, skills and abilities. M. According to Zelman, the fact that students learn only the knowledge necessary to pass a certain exam or write a test task is related to the orientation of the educational system to this approach - "backwash effect (teaching what will pass the test)" [3].

I.D. Frumin emphasizes that the evaluation of the quality of education is very important for the competitiveness of our country.

According to foreign studies, the quality of specialist training depends on three factors: cognitive, affective and objective.

Cognitive factors refer to individual personal characteristics (mind, memory, attention, concentration) that contribute to learning success. Affective factors are an emotional reaction to external circumstances, for example, how strong is the student's motivation to learn, how is his communication within the group developed, does he like the subject being studied. Objective factors are the actual quality of education. If we consider these factors in percentages, then only 25% correspond to moments related to learning, and the rest divide affective and cognitive factors into 25% and 50%, respectively.

Opponents of control conclude that control measures have no practical value. Nevertheless, they recognize that there are disadvantages to denying control, and one of the main ones is the loss of one of the most powerful incentives in the learning process, so other equally powerful means of motivation must be found or renewed [4]. If we consider the issues of supervision, we cannot talk about "rational" motivation, the opposite situation often occurs (in mathematics, this approach is called "with conflict"), students do not seek to increase the effectiveness of their knowledge during the study period, but avoid problems during supervision activities. aspirations are negative motivation.

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